

Our Heritage, Our Stories
Workshop Report

W3: Evaluating Reuse

Background

This workshop aimed to interrogate the potential for 'reuse' on the *Our Heritage, Our Stories* project, approaching this topic in relation to expertise, resources, and data throughout the project. By fostering a comprehensive understanding of the project's structure, objectives, and deliverables, the team assessed how knowledge, skills, and expertise can be effectively redistributed or applied across the project and within the community, as well as how community-generated data might be reused and reconceptualised within the final project Observatory. Understanding each team member's expertise and the datasets available were central to this process, with a key focus on clarifying roles and responsibilities to ensure that everyone knew who to approach for specific elements of the project and how data is being handled across different labs. Furthermore, establishing a shared project vision was a crucial planned outcome from the workshop, with an agreed understanding of how the project ultimately hopes for community data to be reused and recontextualised, including what sort of tools and visualisations we hope to offer in the final project Observatory for communities and the public to access and explore CGDC and its stories. This workshop took place over 3 days, with a half-day on 12th October 2022, a full-day of facilitated sessions on 13th October 2022, and a half-day on 14th October 2022.

Attendees

- **University of Glasgow (UofG):** Lorna Hughes, Marc Alexander, Ewan Hannaford
- **The National Archives (TNA):** Pip Willcox, John Moore, Jenny Bunn, Hazel Jell, Harshad Gupta, Walteri Nybom, Valentina Vavassori
- **University of Manchester (UofM):** Hannah Barker, Goran Nenandic, Riza Batista-Navarro, Stefan Ramsden, Youcef Benkhedda
- **Creative Huddle:** Facilitator for sessions on 13th October.

Workshop aims

- Develop a clear shared understanding of the roles, responsibilities, and expertise of each workstream.
- Establish a shared project vision to guide future project activities and outputs, with agreed activities and tools to foster CGDC reuse.
- Roadmap future data use and reuse, project activities, and communications, with a clear indication of the people responsible for each task.

Key Discussions

Roles and responsibilities

The workshop was framed round an initial reaffirmation of the project's aims and objectives from the project bid, accompanied by an explication of the roles and responsibilities of each lab and team member. Through shared activities and discussion, the project team gained a comprehensive understanding of each individual's expertise

and experience, communication styles, and responsibilities, as well as where these intended to sit within the overall project structure. Possibilities for reusing team expertise in different labs to contribute feedback and advice as 'critical friends' were explored, as well as mapping an overall view of where data is being used and reused across the project and who is responsible for it at each stage.

Figure 1 - Team mapping of data use and reuse on the project

Our Heritage, Our Stories use cases

The OHOS History lab provided a case study exemplifying how community data can be reused and recontextualised to challenge and complement historical narratives, focusing on the Women's Peace Movement (WPM) of the 1980s, particularly at Greenham Common. This highlighted the differing research questions that different audiences might use CGDC to answer:

- **Academic researchers:** Exploring the factors that prevented women from attending protests and the role of both local and international networks in the movement.
- **Community researchers:** Investigating Welsh women's participation and how to preserve the movement's history for modern social justice activism.
- **Family history researchers:** Understanding the personal experiences of relatives involved in the WPM, such as those who participated at Greenham Common or Women for Life on Earth (WFLOE).

To answer these questions a wide variety of sources are available, including the materials of institutional collections (The People's Collection at the National Library of Wales, Glamorgan Archives, and the Commonwealth Library at the University of Bradford contain records, photographs, banners, and personal papers of activists) and Government records (The National Archives offers documents from the Cold War era relating to Greenham Common, with materials from government offices, the Ministry of Defence, and RAF station files). However, CGDC resources – e.g. activist websites, oral history projects, and personal blogs – can provide further and contrasting perspectives. The "Greenham Women Everywhere" project, for instance, offers online resources such as photos, videos, and oral histories to commemorate the movement's 40th anniversary. These sources offer a comprehensive view of the WPM and help researchers uncover the contributions of 'missing' activists, document local and personal experiences, and connect the historical movement to ongoing activism. This case study thus demonstrated how existing data may be reused and recontextualised to provide new research insights and outlined a vision for the potential of CGDC as an invaluable source of hidden stories and histories that the project can uncover.

**OHOS USE CASE:
WOMEN'S PEACE
MOVEMENT
(WPM)**

Figure 2 - Screenshot of OHOS use case presentation

Facilitated sessions – CreativeHuddle

A facilitated session run by CreativeHuddle was designed to establish a shared project vision and establish working patterns and procedures to help achieve this, including outlining roles and responsibilities for data management throughout the project. A high-level description of the project's ultimate objective was collaboratively produced, while team exercises were conducted to help improve team collaboration and working styles. These activities helped to establish a shared understanding of the project's vision and outlined a path for future collaborative working and sharing skills and knowledge.

Figure 3 – Shared team description of overall project objectives

Data Strategy

The project's Data Strategy was discussed extensively, which had been developed in the lead up to the workshop in order to flesh out where data was being used and reused across the project, how data was envisioned to be remixed in the final project Observatory, and who was in charge of these different processes. Data acquisition was agreed to follow this structured Data Strategy, initially utilizing project partner data before expanding to community data sources, ensuring permissions are observed. A number of discussions were held around what sorts of tools the Observatory should provide for different audiences, with academic researchers requiring different capabilities to local historians or members of the public. Also central to these discussions were the types of data the project would receive from communities, what capacity for flexibility in formats and standards the project pipeline should be capable of receiving, and logistics of how data would be processed and passed to different data stores. An overall desire to limit demands on community organisations as far as possible was clearly established, with the team joint in their hope to support as wide an array of formats as feasible and for any conversion efforts to be supported by the team rather than expecting communities to conduct such work. It was also agreed that data would only be used on the project if the team gained permission from the relevant owners/managers of this material, with all data acquired either already available online (in poorly structured formats which make meaningful linking impossible) or provided to us by their owners. The overall aim in data collection was established to collect CGDC that is diverse and fully representative of the languages, communities, and subjects contained within CGDC across the UK.

Engagement Strategy

The project's Engagement Strategy was also discussed extensively, emphasizing stakeholder collaboration to maximize project impact within the rich landscape of CGDC. A Project Advisory Board comprising IRO representatives, digital humanities (DH) practitioners, heritage experts, and TaNC programme representatives was agreed to meet annually, providing strategic advice, progress oversight, and ensuring project outputs have broader applicability and impact. Community and stakeholder engagement was agreed to begin with an initial scoping phase, led by the Archives Lab, to assess existing work from partners like Tate and the National Library of Scotland (NLS). This phase would map current data practices to inform project development, with follow-up activities including open surveys and workshops, inviting input from community groups for case studies, co-design, and feedback. The role of the Community Fund was agreed as being to support community engagement with two initial closed calls for the Community Archives Heritage Group Scotland and Manchester Histories, followed by four open calls. Applications were agreed to be managed through the project website, social media, and partner networks, with guidelines in the OHOS Community Fund Pack. Stakeholder identification was discussed as crucial to the success of the project and effective reuse of CGDC, encompassing TaNC leadership, community data maintainers, researchers, family historians, and technical users. Co-design efforts were agreed upon to engage stakeholders in surveys, workshops, and feedback sessions to develop the Observatory interface. Dissemination and reuse of project insights was decided to occur via the project website, social media, and academic publications, with additional community engagement through events and online platforms.

Reflections

The workshop effectively explored reuse as a central concept to maximize the value and reach of community-generated digital content (CGDC). This focus on reuse was interwoven through discussions on team roles, data strategy, and the project's vision, with a commitment to recontextualizing existing materials for new insights and applications across diverse audiences.

- **Establish roles and responsibilities:** Each team member's role was defined with the objective of supporting CGDC reuse across various project stages. By understanding the unique expertise within each lab and potential 'critical friends' to provide cross-lab feedback, the team established a collaborative approach to ensuring that data collected by one group could be effectively repurposed by another. Mapping data responsibilities further clarified who would oversee and facilitate the reuse of data as it moves through different stages of the project, making reuse a core functional principle.
- **Produce a shared team vision:** During the vision-setting session, facilitated by CreativeHuddle, the team aligned around the goal of enabling widespread reuse of community and historical data. This shared objective shaped the selection of tools and activities specifically designed to allow different audiences—academic researchers, community historians, and the public—to access and recontextualize CGDC for their unique needs. By establishing a high-level commitment to making CGDC resources versatile and adaptable, the team reinforced that reuse should drive all project activities and outputs.
- **Outline a roadmap for use and reuse:** A critical part of the project roadmap was designing a data strategy that facilitates flexible, permission-based data reuse. Plans for data acquisition, led by initial project partner contributions, highlighted the need for adaptable formats and tools to support diverse reuse scenarios. The discussions around CGDC data tools and iterative feedback highlighted the necessity that collected data could be remixed and repurposed effectively for different research questions, themes, and audiences. This underlined the project's intention to create a lasting, reusable repository that benefits from and continues to support the dynamic re-engagement of CGDC resources long after the project's completion.

Through these discussions and planning, the workshop established reuse not just as an outcome but as a guiding principle of OHOS, driving the project's strategic alignment, stakeholder engagement, and data handling.